
Attention based Transformers for Mitosis Domain Generalization in H&E stained WSIs

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ABSTRACT

Digital pathology is increasingly being used in the diagnosis and prognosis of tumors. Detection of increased mitosis is a key component of tumor prognostication for various tumors. While manual interpretation is still the most widely used, it suffers from high variability between pathologists, severely affecting accuracy and reproducibility. Furthermore, this requires significant time and effort from expert pathologists thereby limiting its scalability. Many of the current state-of-the-art methods in digital histopathology are specialized for specific tumors. Such models have limited generalization capability in the case of unseen tissue types and in the case of instrument and staining variations. Hence there is a need for accurate methods for detection of mitotic figures which can generalize well to unseen tissue types and is robust against instrument variability.

1 INTRODUCTION

The practice of pathology where digital imaging is used for the analysis and interpretation of static images, images seen using live streaming as well as whole slide images (WSI) describes some of the main aspects of what is known as digital pathology [1]. The use of digital pathology for enhanced accuracy in the diagnosis and prognosis of tumors is an area of increased interest as evinced by the increased number of recent challenges like MICCAI, ICPR and others. However, despite significant advances in computational pathology, there is still a lack of efficient and effective computer-based tools which are regularly used by pathologists [2].

Mitoses is the process of division of a cell into two daughter cells. This process in normal cells, is symmetric and typical, consisting of 5 stages - interphase, prophase, metaphase, anaphase and telophase. However, in cancer, cell division is mostly

asymmetric resulting in increased cell proliferation. Mitotic cells in the same cancer type appear similar as against mitotic cells from other cancer types [3].

Mitosis detection is a key component of tumor prognostication for various tumors. As expected, increased mitotic count implies high density of mitotic figures and consequently greater chance of tumor proliferation. Currently, the standard method is visual assessment by expert pathologists. Modern deep learning architectures could help provide improved detection accuracies for mitosis to levels close to that of human experts. However, while there may be different methods trained on one tumor/tissue type, the performance of these methods may vary significantly when used on another tumor/tissue type. Furthermore, instrument and staining variability can pose additional challenges in achieving consistent performance. With the aim of addressing the different issues pertaining to automated detection of mitotic figures, there have been different Challenges conducted in the past like TUPAC16 [4], MitoS & Atypia 14 [5], and MIDOG-2021 [6]. The MIDOG 2021 challenge [6] looked at overcoming the domain shift caused by using a different scanner. It was however carried out only on human breast cancer histopathology images.

The MIDOG 2022 challenge [7] looks at developing strategies that address the issue of tissue-related domain-shift, working well across tissue types. There are many factors identified that could affect the performance of deep learning approaches - these include differences in tissue preparation, staining differences across different laboratories, different features and specifications of scanners, and the different sizes and shapes of cells, among others. We have built this deep learning-based algorithm to detect mitotic figures, which we propose to best address most of the above-mentioned factors.

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2 METHODS

In the following, we outline the main steps in our approach.

2.1 Data

For the MIDOG 2022 microscopy domain generalization challenge, we were provided with a training set of digitized microscopy slides from tumor cases obtained from different laboratories and different scanners. The scanners included 3DHistech Panoramic Scan II, Hamamatsu NanoZoomer XR, Aperio ScanScope CS2, Hamamatsu S360, and the Leica GT450. The 6 types of tumors were from human and dog and scanned using five different whole slide scanners to reflect real-world variability as much as possible. The dataset included 150 human breast cancer cases from the first MIDOG challenge, 44 canine lung cancer cases, 55 canine lymphomas, 55 human neuroendocrine tumors, 50 canine cutaneous mast cell tumors, and 49 human melanoma cases leading to a total of 403 cases. The melanoma cases were unlabeled. A preliminary test set to be used for algorithm validation was provided by the MIDOG 2022 organizers, containing 5 cases each of 4 different tumor types which are not part of the final test set. The final test set contains 10 cases each of 10 other tumor types which are not revealed to us, and the majority of those tumor types are not of the those seen during training.

2.2 Data Pre-processing and Augmentation

Train and validation datasets were created using 80:20 split on the 354 annotated images. Based on the labeled training data, 512x512 pixel contextual regions around the mitotic/imposter figures were extracted from each WSI. Multiple contextual regions were extracted for each labeled figure after applying random shift to the context window. For each annotated mitotic patch, we generate two contextual regions while we generate one contextual region for a non-mitotic patch. The contextual regions were added to the annotated regions and an equal number of mitotic and non-mitotic regions are randomly picked to balance the bias in the dataset. Standard augmentation methods such as horizontal flipping, vertical flipping, random rescaling, random cropping, and random rotation are performed to make the model invariant to geometric perturbations. Moreover, Random HSV is also adopted to randomly change the hue, saturation, and value of images in the hue saturation value (HSV) color space, making the model robust to color perturbations.

2.3 DETR based object detection

Detection Transformer (DETR) [8] was trained on the MIDOG 2022 dataset. Resnet50-DC5 backbone

pretrained on ImageNet was selected based on the F1 score on the validation dataset among other DETR backbones viz. Resnet101, Resnet50 and Resnet101-DC5. Adam optimizer was used for optimization with initial learning rate of backbone and DETR set to 1e-04 and 1e-05 respectively. We chose the default cross entropy for label loss over focal loss since our training data was balanced. The hyperparameters of DETR were chosen using Optuna hyperparameter optimization framework [9]. For the test WSI images, using a sliding window with overlay of 50 pixels, cropped regions of size 512x512 pixels were extracted. Each cropped region was fed to the trained DETR model. The DETR output consisted of the identified objects and their associated class probabilities. All mitotic predictions with class probability greater than or equal to 0.85 were directly included in the output with mitotic class label. For the preliminary test phase as well as the final test phase, we trained the DETR model on the entire labelled training data of 354 images. All models were implemented using Pytorch and all experiments were performed on Nvidia DGX A100 GPU cards with 40GB memory.

3 RESULTS

The performance of this approach measured using the F1 score is shown in the Table 1. Table 1 shows the performance using F1 score of our approach and the baselines provided by the organizers on the preliminary test set across four tumor types and on the validation set. Our model outperforms the baselines and generalizes across the tumor types on the preliminary test set.

Table 1. F1 score for this model on Challenge data

Model	F1 (Validation set)	F1 (Preliminary test set)				
		Total	T1	T2	T3	T4
Our Model	0.804	0.760	0.750	0.795	0.708	0.810
Baseline 2	-	0.715	0.744	0.732	0.692	0.711
Baseline 1	-	0.629	0.753	0.608	0.585	0.743

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